

Supporting Material to accompany:

Positional isomerism in the N^N ligand: How much difference does a methyl group make in [Cu(P[^]P)(N[^]N)]⁺ complexes?

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Fig. S1. ESI-MS of [Cu(POP)(5,6'-Me₂bpy)][PF₆].

Fig. S2. ESI-MS of [Cu(xantphos)(5,6'-Me₂bpy)][PF₆].

Figure S3. ^1H NMR spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(5,6'\text{-Me}_2\text{bpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ in acetone- d_6 (500 MHz, 298 K). * = residual acetone- d_5 ; ** = H_2O / HOD ; *** = CH_2Cl_2 .

Figure S4. ^1H NMR spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(5,6'\text{-Me}_2\text{bpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ in acetone- d_6 (500 MHz, 298 K). * = residual acetone- d_5 overlapping with the signal for $\text{H}^{\text{Me-A5}}$; ** = H_2O / HOD ; + = CH_2 of Et_2O . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S5. Part of the $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(5,6'\text{-Me}_2\text{bpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ in acetone- d_6 (500 MHz, 298 K). Scale: δ/ppm .

Figure S6. HMBC spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(5,6'\text{-Me}_2\text{bpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ in acetone- d_6 (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz ^{13}C , 298 K). Scale: δ/ppm .

Figure S7. HMBC spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(5,6'\text{-Me}_2\text{bpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ in acetone- d_6 (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz ^{13}C , 298 K). * = residual acetone- d_5 ; + = CH_2Cl_2 . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S8. HMQC spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(5,6'\text{-Me}_2\text{bpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ in acetone- d_6 (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz ^{13}C , 298 K). Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S9. HMBC spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(5,6'\text{-Me}_2\text{bpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ in acetone- d_6 (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz ^{13}C , 298 K). * = Residual acetone- d_5 overlapping with the signal for $\text{H}^{\text{Me-A5}}$; ** = H_2O / HOD ; + = CH_2 of Et_2O . Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S10. Part of the NOESY spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(5,6'\text{-Me}_2\text{bpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ in acetone- d_6 (500 MHz ^1H , 298 K).

Table S1. Values of A_1 , A_2 , τ_1 and τ_2 for the biexponential fit to the decay using the equation: $\tau = \sum A_i \tau_i / \sum A_i$

Compound	A_1	τ_1	A_2	τ_2	τ
[Cu(POP)(5,6'-Me ₂ bpy)][PF ₆]	0.6612	8.236	0.2997	2.463	6.435
[Cu(xantphos)(5,6'-Me ₂ bpy)][PF ₆]	0.614	6.384	0.3115	2.12	4.949